

Transcriptomic Profiling of ABX464-mediated Anti-Viral Immunity in Macrophages

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Abstract

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is a virus that weakens the human immune system that leads to acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), which renders individuals more susceptible to other infections and diseases. There are currently no available cures of HIV, so more research is needed to develop cost-effective methods to seek therapeutic interventions. The purpose of this review article is to discuss the mechanistic impacts of ABX464, which is an anti-HIV drug that has been shown to decelerate HIV biogenesis. Using a publicly available database of RNA sequence repository, it can be surmised that ABX464 can increase antiviral function in macrophages by limiting the flux of major histocompatibility class I pathway. This could potentially limit the proliferation and activation of T-cells, which would be beneficial in the context of anti-HIV response, given that HIV primarily targets T-cells for its growth and proliferation. These observations indicate that ABX464 can potentially exert pleiotropic methods of suppressing viral biogenesis and activity.

Keywords: HIV, RNA-sequencing, Inflammation, Innate and Adaptive Immunity

1. Introduction

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is a retrovirus that attacks the human body's immune system. If not treated quickly enough, HIV leads to the progression of AIDS (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome), which is characterized as the full weakening of the immune system (5). Currently, there is no available cure or eradication procedures, but with proper care and treatment, HIV can be controlled. There are several well-characterized HIV

therapeutics, including fusion inhibitors, HIV reverse transcriptase inhibitors, protease inhibitors, integrase inhibitors, and viral capsid inhibitors (14). But HIV treatments are very expensive, and many HIV-patients unfortunately pass away without proper medication (18). In fact, as of 2022, over 39 million people across the world are HIV-positive, and over 630,000 patients have died of HIV-related illnesses (5,18). Therefore, more research is needed to develop cost-effective treatment strategies for HIV and AIDS.

ABX464 is one of the several anti-HIV drugs developed by Abivax. In their original studies, ABX464 was intended to serve as a treatment for ulcerative colitis that has been shown to upregulate the expression of a miRNA, miR-124, leading to a dampening of the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-6, TNF α , IL-17, and MCP-1 (1). When colorectal biopsies of patients were treated with ABX464, between seven-to-ten fold increase in miR-124 was observed. Most importantly, ABX464 doesn't appear to cause non-specific splicing of cellular genes, which demonstrates the specificity in its mechanism of action (1).

Recently, ABX464 has been shown to work effectively against HIV. One study has taken HIV patients and collected their peripheral CD4⁺ T-cells for drug efficacy and analysis (4). ABX464 was shown to inhibit HIV RNA biogenesis, and thus, researchers wanted to conduct a clinical trial measuring HIV reservoir and transcription initiation in the presence of ABX464. These patients consumed 150 mg of ABX464 for 4 weeks. Total and intact HIV DNA and initiated, 5' elongated, unspliced, polyadenylated, and multiple-spliced HIV transcripts were quantified at week 0, 4, and 8 using ddPCR. By 8th week, researchers observed significantly reduced levels of HIV DNA and initiated HIV RNA transcripts per million CD4⁺ T-cells upon ABX464 treatment. This led to the conclusion that ABX464 can be a potential long-term HIV treatment that can be coupled with other therapeutic interventions (13,19).

ABX464 however, still has a long way to go. Current prevailing treatment methods against HIV is the antiretroviral therapy (ART) using various anti-HIV drugs, such as bictegravir/tenofovir alafenamide/emtricitabine regimen (6). However, many of these cocktails have been shown to exhibit residual inflammation associated with non-AIDS related morbidity and mortality. Thus, measures of inflammation and immune activation are great predictors of disease progression in HIV-infected individuals. Mucosal damage to the gastrointestinal (GI) tract with resulting microbial translocation significantly contributes to the heightened and persistent chronic inflammation and immune activation to HIV infection, which may contribute to viral persistence during ART (6,9).

Recent study in a colitis model has implicated that ABX464 can reduce the colonic production of the inflammatory cytokines—IL-6, TNF α , and MCP1—while inducing the gene expression of IL-22, a cytokine involved in colitis tissue repair (2). Therefore, researchers believed that ABX464 not only suppresses pro-inflammatory responses that reduce hypersensitivity in the patient's immune system, but can combat viral burden via enhanced expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-22 (2).

This research report utilizes a publicly-available RNA seq database that has been deposited by the same research group that published their findings on ABX464's induction of IL-22 in a colitis model. Researchers used a gram negative microbial product, known as lipopolysaccharide (LPS) to establish a pro-inflammatory stimulus in bone marrow-derived macrophages (BMDMs), followed by treatment with a vehicle control or ABX464. The purpose of this report is to explore the effects of ABX464 in LPS-induced BMDMs in various categories of inflammatory and anti-inflammatory genes that were not thoroughly explored in Chebli et. al (2017).

2. Methodology

The methodology for this manuscript was partially adapted from Chebli et. al (2017). Outlined below summarizes the core materials and methods used to generate the RNA sequencing database. This manuscript explores the following gene classification: Anti-viral genes (e.g., *Ifit1*, *Mx-1*, *Ch25h*, *Isg20*, and *Parp12*), pro-inflammatory genes (e.g., *Cxcl1*, *Irf1*, *Stat1*, and *Tnfa*), anti-inflammatory genes (e.g., *Il13*, *Pdl2*, *Cd206*, and *Cd163*), and antigen-presentation genes (e.g., *H2k1*, *Sec61*, *Tap1*, and *Tap2*).

IFIT-1 is a viral RNA-binding protein that specifically binds to the single-stranded RNA bearing 5' triphosphate group, thereby acting as a sensor of viral mRNAs (12). MX-1 is an interferon-induced gene that blocks viral transcription and replication, particularly the influenza virus (20). ISG20 is also thought to induce the degradation of viral RNA (24). PARP12 spearheads both the inhibition and the degradation of viral mRNAs (22). CH25H is an interferon-stimulating gene located in the endoplasmic reticulum that produces an oxysterol called 25HC, which has been shown to abrogate viral entry into cells (16). All these genes collectively play a pivotal role in minimizing viral growth and pathogenesis.

Both IRF1 and STAT1 are transcriptional factors that respond to inflammatory cytokines to produce an antimicrobial response (8,25). CXCL1 is a pro-inflammatory chemokine known to attract neutrophils toward the site of infection, while TNFa is a proinflammatory cytokine produced by various innate immune cells to trigger production of inflammatory chemotaxis (25).

Both CD163 and CD206 are surface markers that distinguish a M2-polarized macrophage (26). Macrophages are broadly classified as either M1 (pro-inflammatory) or M2 (anti-inflammatory), depending on the stimulus (26). Arg1 is a metabolic enzyme found in the urea cycle that removes excess nitrogen that leads to suppression of T-cells (by limiting the amount of nutrients for T-cell activation and growth (4). Fizz1 helps regulate T-cell

differentiation and eosinophil migration (7). Mgl2 is a surface-marker lectin that fosters immunosuppression and inhibits Th1 polarization (Th1 is a subtype of helper T-cell that fosters inflammatory reactions) (3). PDL-2 is an inhibitory ligand of cytotoxic CD8⁺ T-cells (21). Finally, IL-13 is a cytokine that primes immature macrophage for M2 polarization (17). H2-K1 is a major, polymorphic subunit of the MHC class I receptor that mediates endogenously processed antigen presentation into CD8⁺ T-cells (23,10). Sec61 is a component of the ER that facilitates protein translation, post-translational modification, and protein folding, which ultimately assembles the MHC subunits together (11). TAP1 and TAP2 are crucial proteins that play a role in loading viral peptides onto the groove of MHC class I molecules prior to surface presentation (15).

2.1 Aim of the Study

The purpose of this study was to interrogate whether ABX464 could bolster antiviral immunity in innate immune cells, such as bone marrow derived macrophages, via altering expression of genes implicated in antiviral response.

2.2 Research Design

This manuscript is more of an exploratory research that utilizes a publicly accessible RNA sequencing database to generate an alternative conclusion that was not explored by the authors that have originally deposited the database. The independent variable represents the different treatment groups (e.g., DMSO +/- ABX464 and LPS +/- ABX464), while the dependent variables represent the total counts of mRNA representing a specific gene.

2.3 Hypothesis

In addition to ABX464-mediated suppression of inflammatory markers, this manuscript aims to uncover alternative classes of immune-related genes that help potentiate antiviral response. The central hypothesis is that ABX464 can augment macrophages' antiviral effector function by limiting MHC class I presentation to T-cells, which limits T-cell activation and

subsequent propagation of HIV particles. The null hypothesis is that ABX464 has no effect on the macrophage's antiviral immunity in the context of MHC presentation.

2.4 Consent and Ethical Considerations

All ethical considerations were followed for the current study. All of the data used in this research paper was derived from a publicly available RNA sequencing database on Gene Expression Omnibus (2). All mice experimentations performed during the study followed the guidelines of the European Community and the French National Committee.

2.5 Sample

Chebli et. al (2017) does not address the total number of experimental models used in the experiments. The genetic background of the mice is C57BL6.

2.6 Scales used/tools used/instruments used

Microsoft Excel was used as the main platform to generate all of the figures outlined in this manuscript.

2.7 Data Collection Procedure

Fresh bone marrow precursor cells from mice femurs were cultured in 9 days in the presence of GM-CSF for terminal differentiation into macrophages. Cell cultures were subsequently treated with either DMSO or ABX464, followed by an additional stimulation with LPS for 6h. Cell cultures were harvested for mRNA extraction, followed by reverse transcription to create a cDNA library. Quantitative real time PCR was then performed using SYBR Green on select target genes (2). Each sample was normalized by three housekeeping genes—GUS, HPRT, and TFIID.

For the rest of this research paper, FPKM (Fragments Per Kilobase per Million mapped fragments) for select immune-related genes were imported from the Gene Expression Omnibus database, and they were graphed on Microsoft Excel for quantitative analysis. There

are four total independent variables: 1) DMSO & Nonstimulated, 2) ABX46 & Nonstimulated, 3) DMSO & LPS (6h), and 4) ABX464 & LPS (6h).

3. Results

First, the research paper explores the gene expression program of those that are involved in antiviral response. After all, ABX464 is a potential anti-HIV therapy, and it would be greatly useful to ascertain the changes in genes that regulate antiviral activity. To address this, following genes were observed: IFIT1, IFN-b, ISG20, MX-1, PARP12, and CH25H. As expected, LPS stimulation increases the expression of IFIT-1, ISG20, CH25H, and MX-1, supporting the concept that these cells are engaging interferon-stimulating targets upon microbial exposure (**Figure 1**). Interestingly, PARP12 expression is downregulated in response to LPS, which may imply some degree of signal specificity. However, when LPS stimulation alone is compared with ABX464 co-stimulation, it doesn't appear that ABX464 changes the gene expression of these ISGs (**Figure 1**). These observations suggest that LPS-priming of BMDMs does not necessarily improve the efficacy of ABX464 in terms of antiviral gene signatures.

Next, the research paper follows up with genes involved in both pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory responses. Pro-inflammatory genes included: CXCL1, IRF1, STAT1, and TNF α . As expected, LPS stimulation also led to an increase of these pro-inflammatory genes (**Figure 2**). But just like the antiviral response genes, ABX464 co-stimulation also doesn't seem to alter the expression of these pro-inflammatory genes, suggesting that ABX464 does not necessarily converge on inflammatory signaling to mediate antiviral response against HIV.

Anti-inflammatory genes that were studied in this research report were: Arg1, CD163, CD206, Fizz1, Mgl2, PDL-2, and IL-13. In this set of genes, there were a few interesting trends. First, IL-13 expression was unaltered with LPS or ABX464 alone, but only when they were co-stimulated, we observed a synergy in IL-13 expression (**Figure 3**). This may suggest that macrophages are readily priming themselves to become converted into M2 polarized states when stimulated with an anti-HIV drug. This could be a therapeutic benefit to reduce inflammatory stress during a viral infection. Similar trend was observed with PDL-2, which also suggests that ABX464 is trying to systematically limit the activation and proliferation of cytotoxic CD8 T-cells (**Figure 3**). Despite the increased expression of IL-13 however, it

doesn't appear that the expression of CD163, CD206, and Mgl2 correlate (**Figure 4**). This could be due to the fact that LPS stimulation typically favors the conversion of macrophages into M1 pro-inflammatory state, which effectively antagonizes any cellular attempt to polarize into an anti-inflammatory, alternative state.

Finally, the research paper investigated genes involved in antigen presentation pathways between the innate and adaptive immune system, specifically the major histocompatibility class I (MHC class I) pathway, as this pertains to endogenous, viral infection. These genes include: H2-K1, Sec61, TAP1, and TAP2. The expression of both H2-K1 and Sec61 seems to be unaltered between LPS alone versus LPS plus ABX464 co-stimulation (**Figure 5**). However, it does seem to appear that TAP1 and TAP2 seem to have reduced expression when co-stimulated with LPS and ABX464, compared to LPS alone (**Figure 5**). This implies that when a macrophage is primed with an inflammatory signal (a proxy for viral infection),

ABX464 treatment can thereby reduce the presentation of viral peptide antigens into MHC class I, which abrogates the activation of CD8+ T-cells.

4. Discussion

This research paper studies the transcriptomic signature of macrophages responding to a pro-inflammatory stimulus, LPS, coupled with a potential anti-HIV drug, ABX464. While ABX464 has been experimentally shown to bolster anti-inflammatory response in various cell types, it doesn't appear to significantly exert a profound effect in these BMDMs. One possibility is that BMDMs are *in vitro* derived cells from primary hematopoietic stem cells, and depending on the conditioned media and the type of growth factors and cytokines (e.g., macrophage stimulating factor, MCF) used for differentiation, these BMDMs may have acquired some degree of resistance to anti-inflammatory activation. Overall, it can be concluded that there isn't sufficient information to conclude that ABX464 increases or decreases the gene expression profile of antiviral-related genes, as well as pro-inflammatory

genes. However, it is interesting to note that certain anti-inflammatory markers, such as IL-13 and PDL-2, were upregulated synergistically with LPS plus ABX464. This validates a previous finding that ABX464 can bolster anti-inflammatory responses, when coupled to a pro-inflammatory stimulus. This could be an advantageous response for the host cells by limiting the spread of pro-inflammatory burden.

Likewise, it's interesting that both TAP1 and TAP2 expressions are lowered upon co-stimulation of LPS and ABX464. As expected, LPS stimulation mimics a systemic viral infection, which explains why all of the MHC presentation pathway genes are upregulated. But ABX464 treatment can potentially limit viral antigen presentation by slowing down the loading of the viral-derived peptide onto nascent MHC surrogate. In an evolutionary standpoint, this might not necessarily be advantageous to the host. After all, shouldn't the host immune system maximize the adaptive immunity as much as possible by increasing antigen presentation?

While it's reasonable to believe that enhanced antigen presentation equates to augmented antiviral response, this isn't that simple. One complication of an HIV infection is that HIV specifically targets proliferating T-cells. Therefore, if host cells were to present antigens to T-cells and prime their activation, it could be possible that more HIV particles can be unleashed. It is important to remember that HIV is a retrovirus that integrates its genome directly into the host cell's genome, meaning the HIV genome is permanently part of the host. Therefore, it could potentially risk a double-edged sword phenomenon, in which more proliferating CD8 T-cells can enhance HIV proliferation.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research paper demonstrates a highly reductionist approach method of considering the molecular mechanism of ABX464-mediated antiviral reprogramming in response to pro-inflammatory stimulus. It's difficult to assess if these transcriptomic changes

are translatable to *in vivo* clinical relevance. After all, macrophages are highly plastic cells, and their phenotypes are characterized by various factors, such as the genetic background of the murine model, cell culturing conditions, drug pharmacology (i.e., PK/PD, lipophilicity, half-life, clearance rate, etc.), and cellular heterogeneity. But all studies ultimately need a starting point, and macrophages are great tools that help deconvolute initial molecular mechanisms. After all, macrophages play a versatile role in both the innate and adaptive immune effector functions.

One potential mechanism is that ABX464 reduces macrophage's antigen presentation capacity to limit T-cell activation & proliferation, thus disfavoring viral pathogenesis. Whether ABX464 directly or indirectly interferes with antigen presentation remains enigmatic and will warrant further studies. It could be possible that ABX464-induced upregulation of miRNA-124 could target other classes of genes, including those involved in the antigen presentation pathway. Of course, there are dozens of signaling pathways that were not explored in the research paper, and it would be interesting to study how ABX464 stimulation alters the transcriptomics in other effector functions.

6. Limitations

Macrophages only represent a subset of the immune cell population, and therefore, it would be useful to extend this study into other relevant cell types, such as dendritic cells, B-cells, and T-cells. Furthermore, while the RNA seq database provides an umbrella overview of the changes in transcriptomics in response to external stimuli, changes in gene expression are not often correlated to changes in the cellular phenotype. More rigorous meta studies, such as proteomics and exomics are needed to fully deconvolute this enigma behind ABX464's mechanism of action in terms of HIV response.

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